

D1.2 – Quality and Risk Management Plan

Executive Summary

The objective of quality and risk management is to establish and enforce effective management and quality procedures that will result in efficient monitoring of the project resource and high-quality project reports. Quality and risk management will necessitate the definition of a Quality Plan (tools and metrics), including specific measures to follow up the fulfillment of key performance indicators (KPI) and close monitoring of the risk next to the development of contingency plans. At each step of the project, it will be required to verify that standards, procedures, and metrics are defined, applied, and evaluated.

Keywords

Quality plan, risk management, metrics, performance, contingency plan.

Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Grant Agreement number 101094270. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This document and its content are the property of the PALOMERA Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the PALOMERA project and this document are properly referenced. Each PALOMERA beneficiary is invited to use this document in conformity with the PALOMERA Consortium and Grant Agreement provisions.

Document Identification

Workpackage	WP1		
Lead Beneficiary	BE1 - OPERAS	Lead Author	Céline BITOUNE
Contributors	Céline Bitoune (OPERAS)		
Reviewers	Yannick Legré (OPERAS) Sy Holsinger (OPERAS)		
Type	R - Document, report	Dissemination level	Public (P)
Status	Draft (Under EC review)	Due date	2023/06/30
Version ¹	D1.1 V1.5	Submission date	2023/07/26

Document history

Version	Date	Change editors name	Changes
1.0	2023/05/15	Céline Bitoune	First draft
1.1	2023/07/20	Céline Bitoune	Draft complete for review
1.2	2023/07/21	Yannick Legré, Sy Holsinger	Review
1.3	2023/07/25	Céline Bitoune	Correction input from reviewers
1.4	2023/07/25	Céline Bitoune	Final draft with integration of comments
1.5	2023/07/26	Céline Bitoune	Final Version

Quality control

Role	Name (Beneficiary short name)	Approval date
Project manager (Quality)	Céline Bitoune (OPERAS)	2023/07/26

¹ Use 2.0, 2.1, etc. if the version is updated after the EC rejection.

Table of Content

TABLE OF ACRONYMS	4
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. QUALITY MANAGEMENT	6
2.1. QUALITY PLAN	7
2.2. MANAGING QUALITY	8
2.2.1. MANAGEMENT OF DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES	8
2.2.2. COORDINATION OF THE PROJECT'S PERIODIC AND FINAL REPORTS PREPARATION	8
2.2.3. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI)	8
2.2.4. PROJECT MANAGEMENT KPIS OVERVIEW	10
2.3. CONTROLLING QUALITY	11
2.3.1. REPORTING QUALITY AND RISK STATUS	11
2.3.2. ORGANISATION OF PROJECT WORKING SPACE	11
2.3.3. PERIOD 1 DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES	12
2.3.4. IMPLEMENTED CHANGES TO THE DESCRIPTION OF ACTION	13
3. RISK MANAGEMENT	14
3.1. RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESS	14
3.2. RISK IDENTIFICATION & RISK REGISTRY	14
3.3. RISK ANALYSIS	16
3.4. RISK MITIGATION	17
3.5. RISK CONTROL & REVIEW	18
4. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS	18
APPENDIX 1 - DELIVERABLE CHECKLIST, GUIDELINES FOR AUTHOR AND REVIEWER	19
APPENDIX 2 - PM01 DELIVERABLE AND MILESTONES REVIEW	21
APPENDIX 3 - PM02 INTERMEDIATE AND PERIODIC REPORTING	26
APPENDIX 4 – EU-FIN PROJECT MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES	29

Tables and figures

FIGURE 1 QUALITY MANAGEMENT	7
FIGURE 2 EU-FIN PROJECT MANAGEMENT	9
FIGURE 3 PALOMERA SHARED DRIVE	12
FIGURE 4 RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESS	14
FIGURE 5 SLIDE TEMPLATE ON WORK PROGRESS	15
TABLE 1 PCT INTERNAL MANAGEMENT REVIEW	8
TABLE 2 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)	10
TABLE 3 RISK REGISTRY	16
TABLE 4 RISK MATRIX	17
TABLE 5 RISK CONTROL	18

Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	
ALLEA	European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
AMU	Université D'Aix Marseille
CC 0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DACH	Deutschland (Germany), Austria, Confœderatio Helvetica (Switzerland)
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
ED&I	Equity, Diversity & Inclusivity
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
ExCom	Executive Committee
FAIR	Findable. Accessible. Interoperable. Reusable.
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
M#	Project Month <number>
MWS	Max Weber Stiftung
NB	Nota bene
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Book Network

OABT	OAPEN OA Books Toolkit
OAeBU	Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OATP	Open Access Tracking Project
OBP	Open Book Publishers
OER	Open Educational Resource
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OS	Open Science
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (while in this document it will be referred to as Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan)
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors
PIMS	Project Information Management System
RFO	Research Funding Organisations
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
SPARC Europe	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UGOE	Georg August Universität Göttingen
UC	University of Coimbra
UNIBI	University of Bielefeld
WP#	Work Package <number>
ZRC SAZU	The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

1. Introduction

This deliverable defines the quality and risk management for the Palomera project. The task within WP1 falls under the responsibility of the Project Manager. Procedures, processes, and guidelines are implemented to ensure the monitoring and assessment of progress and results across the project in accordance with the quality plan. The document describes the tools and metrics that will be applied in these processes to measure the fulfillment of the key performance indicators (KPIs). This task will also perform risk identification, analysis, and control, to raise awareness and take a proactive approach to prevent the consequence of risk occurrence. Both quality and risk management shall reduce mistakes, recommend changes for improvement and save time and cost to ensure that project objectives are met with success.

2. Quality Management

Quality management relies on processes, procedures, and responsibilities to ensure consistency and control in producing the project outputs.

Quality management comprises three quality processes:

- 1) The Quality plan identifies the project's quality requirements and sets the procedures to manage and validate the quality.
- 2) Managing quality is a process to ensure and monitor the progress of the tasks and reports in compliance with the descriptions in the Grant Agreement and conform to the quality requirements previously defined.
- 3) Controlling quality through monitoring, checking, and comparing metrics with the target base will quantify the project achievements and reveal deviations.

Figure 1 Quality management

2.1. Quality Plan

In Palomera, the quality plan has been defined as part of two deliverables to be submitted within the first 4 months of the project:

- 1) D1.1 “Internal rules and procedures to the consortium” defines the internal communication tools, sets the document repository and the collaborative space, determines the monitoring of the project resource, and provides a summary of the deliverable review process and checklist.
- 2) D5.2 “Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence,” which represents the PALOMERA project’s visual identity, Communication Kit, and Social Media Presence and guides all the project partners in the communication and dissemination activities.

The quality plan has been extended with two procedures:

- 1) “PM01² Deliverable and milestones review procedure” and “deliverable checklist guide” are both attached in Appendix 1 and 2 and,
- 2) “PM02³ Intermediate and Periodic Reporting” is attached in Appendix 3.
It guides partners to complete project reporting and, to the Executive Committee (ExCom), to review the data collected to the KPIs defined.

² Project Management procedure # 01

³ Project Management procedure # 02

In addition, several internal project management reviews are planned in periods 1 and 2:

PCT⁴ internal management review	
Period 1	
Deliverables and milestones	All deliverables and milestones have been reviewed before the submission on the EU portal (Appendix 1)
Financial and effort review	M7 (Intermediate report M1-M6), M9 (periodic report)
Metrics and KPIs review	M9
Risk review	M9 (during the preparation of the periodic report)
Period 2	
Deliverables and milestones	All deliverables and milestones will be reviewed before the submission on the EU portal (Appendix 1)
Financial and effort review	M19 (Intermediate report M10-M18), M24 (periodic report)
Metrics and KPIs review	M18, M24
Risk review	M18

Table 1 PCT internal management review

2.2. Managing Quality

2.2.1. Management of deliverables and milestones

The deliverable process, including quality control, has been described in deliverable D1.1 as part of the internal rules and procedures description. It has been uploaded in Zenodo⁵ on 27th April 2023. The PM01 Deliverable and milestones review procedure and the deliverable checklist are attached in Appendix 1 and 2.

2.2.2. Coordination of the project's periodic and final reports preparation

The project's periodic reports will require a specific process and schedule to ensure active collaboration of the work package leader and timely delivery of the project's periodic report and beneficiaries' financial statements. It will primarily involve the work package leaders and the PCT.

2.2.3. Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

In Palomera, the monitoring of the project activities and outputs is done through three sets of KPIs:

⁴ Project Coordination Team

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7871197>

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

- 1) The achievement of project objectives, divided into 5 specific objectives (SO), will be measured by the timely submission of the associated deliverables as listed in the Grant Agreement⁶.
 - a) Leader: Project Coordination Team (PCT)
- 2) The monitoring of dissemination and engagement activities (KPIs and KERs) has been defined as part of the deliverable “D5.1 – Dissemination, outreach, engagement, and exploitation plan” so-called the PEDR⁷.
 - a) Leader: WP5
- 3) The KPIs defined in the overview provided in the next paragraph (2.2.4) will assess project governance, management, and monitoring of the resources, collected in a dedicated project management tool⁸.
 - a) Leader: Project Coordination Team (PCT)

The screenshot displays the EU-fin project management interface. The top navigation bar includes 'EU-fin', 'Project', 'User Management', 'Management', and 'Setup'. The left sidebar lists various menu items under categories like 'Reporting Costs', 'Planning Budgets', 'Pivots', 'Dashboards', and 'Standard reports'. The main content area features three dropdown menus for selecting a participant, interim period, and work package. On the right, there is a status section for 'Status interim period:' with a 'Submitted by participant:' field and a 'Submit All' button.

Figure 2 EU-fin project management

⁶ GA Page 92-93

⁷ Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

⁸ EU-fin, see guidelines in Appendix 4

2.2.4. Project management KPIs overview

The overall project management and achievement will be measured through 5 KPIs, gathering inputs from 1 to 4 metrics. For some metrics, the project has defined a performance measurement based on three compared values: **Baseline** (minimum value or maximum deviation accepted), **Target** (expected value or acceptable deviation), and **Stretch** (beyond expectation or 100%)

KPI #	KPI 1	KPI 2	KPI 3 ^[1]	KPI 4 ^[1]	KPI 5 ^[1]
KPI name	Achievement of all project objectives	Implementation of sound project management	Establishment of project governance	Use of the resource	Use of the budget
Definition	Timely submission of the associated deliverables	Regular and effective collaboration within the management team	Organisation of General Assembly (GA) meetings as planned	Uses of the person months as planned in the DoA	Uses of the budget as planned in the DoA
Metric 1	% of timely (+/- 30 days) submission	setup of a collaborative space ⁹	# of GA organised	Deviation per work package	Deviation per work package
Target	90%	implementation by M2	2 meetings	B<= 30%; T<=10%; S<=5%	B<= 20%; T<=10%; S=0%
Metric 2	% of milestones delivered on time	provision of a project database	Participation to the GA	Deviation per beneficiary	Deviation per beneficiary
Target	100%	implementation by M2	quorum reached (B=67%; T=>80%; S=>90%)	B<= 30%; T<=10%; S<=5%	B<= 20%; T<=10%; S=0%
Metric 3	-	regular meeting of the work package leaders and PCT	-	-	Monitoring of travel budgets
Target	-	2 meetings per month	-	-	B<= 20%; T<=10%; S=0%
Metric 4	-	-	-	-	Monitoring of other costs budgets
Target	-	-	-	-	B<= 20%; T<=10%; S=0%
Frequency	M9, M18, M24	M9, M18, M24	M8, M23	M6, M9, M18, M24	M6, M9, M18, M24

^[1] **B** = baseline; **T** = target; **S** = stretch

Table 2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

⁹ Project Information Management System (PIMS)

2.3. Controlling quality

The control quality process collects and monitors project metrics. It will provide metrics on project achievements compared to the work planned or another baseline as appropriate. The metrics collection will be organized in an Excel spreadsheet and published in confluence (Table 2 inserted above).

2.3.1. Reporting quality and risk status

Based on the assessment and potential deviation, suggestions for improvement and corrective actions shall be reported and agreed upon at the Executive Committee (ExCom), where the PCT and WP leaders participate. Additional meetings shall be organized to perform assessments during the internal management review planned in the PCT internal management review table.

2.3.2. Organisation of project working space

Available from month 1, the Project Information Management System (PIMS) has been implemented in Confluence. The project partners can structure, organise, collaborate, and share documents in this web-based wiki. Among 29 individuals invited, 22 actively use the project confluence space.

In addition, a document repository has also been organized in Google shared drive to grant better access to Palomera documentation, fostering collaboration while guaranteeing access control to project members only. In shared drives, ownership is defined at the project level or as a team within the project rather than as an individual. Therefore, if members leave, the files stay in the shared drive, avoiding potential data loss, and the team can keep sharing information.

As of today, 76 people are registered and actively using the repository.

Name	Last modified	File size
00-legal documents, GA, CA, BUDGET	Nov 15, 2022	—
01-Project resource monitoring	Nov 15, 2022	—
02-Gantt, Deliverables & Milestones	Nov 15, 2022	—
03-Shared presentations	Jan 26, 2023	—
04-Project reporting Periods	Jan 26, 2023	—
05-Palomera Design folder	Jan 26, 2023	—
WP1 Coordination and Management	Nov 15, 2022	—
WP2 Building the Knowledge Base	Apr 13, 2023	—
WP3 Analysing the Knowledge Base	Nov 15, 2022	—
WP4 Recommendations and resources	Nov 15, 2022	—
WP5 Communication, dissemination, engagement and validation	Nov 15, 2022	—

Figure 3 Palomera shared drive

2.3.3. Period 1 deliverables and milestones

During the first quarter, 5 deliverables were planned. Two were delivered a month later (WP1) due to limited resources and a focus on implementing the early processes and procedures for project management and the Project Information Management System (PIMS). And therefore, the delayed deliverables, including this one, are documentation of what has already been put in place.

WPs	Deliverables		Milestones	
	#	Delay in days	#	Delay in days
WP1	D1.1	27 days	MS1	0
	D1.2	26 days		
	D1.3	14 days		
WP2	-	-	MS2	19
WP3	-	-	-	-
WP4	-	-	-	-
WP5	D5.1	2 days		
	D5.2	0		

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

2.3.4. Implemented changes to the description of action

Since the start of the project, through the Executive Committee (ExCom), several changes have been identified and implemented to perform the activities planned in the Description of Action (DoA).

- 1) Update on the Gantt chart:
 - a. Few activities/tasks have been identified to start earlier,
 - b. Deliverables D4.1 and D4.4 have been inserted in the GANTT (Policy briefs).
- 2) Monitoring of the use of resources: in WP3, WP4, and WP5 person months have been distributed per task due to the different timelines of the tasks and to enable more accurate reporting on the use of resources.
- 3) Change at the beneficiary level: redistribution of efforts and budget has been required to mitigate the departure of key staff.

WP no	Task no	Task name	Start month	End month	Updated timeline
WP3	T3.1	Data coding, enrichment, and preparations for analysis	M6	M21	Move forward from M12 and extended to M14
WP3	T3.2	Conduct analysis	M9	M21	Moved forward from M14
WP4	T4.1	Recommendations for institutional strategies and funder policies for open access books	M15	M24	Postponed from M12
WP4	T4.2	Resources to support institutional strategies and funder policies for open access books	M2	M24	Move forward from M12, WP started at M9
WP5	T5.2	Outreach and Engagement with all stakeholders	M1	M24	Move forward from M21

3. Risk management

3.1. Risk management process

The Executive Committee (ExCom) monitors risks related to the project implementation and proposes timely mitigation measures and corrective actions according to the following process workflow:

Step 1: risk identification

Step 2: risk analysis & mitigation; propose one or more scenarios for each risk

Step 3: risk control (identify owner and supporter, set a review plan)

Figure 4 Risk management process

3.2. Risk identification & Risk registry

Risk Identification

A risk is defined as an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a damaging (threats) or positive (opportunities) effect on a project's objectives¹⁰. In Palomera, the risk management process has been limited to threats.

The first set of risks associated with Palomera's objectives has been identified in the project proposal. Following a bottom-up approach, risks will be identified in cooperation with work package leaders during the bi-monthly Executive Committee (ExCom) meetings through the work package report.

¹⁰ Source: PMBOK <https://www.pmi.org/pmbok-guide-standards/foundational/pmbok>

In addition, during the risk review meetings, the project will monitor the potential appearance of new threats and record them in the risk registry as part of the risk control process.

Figure 5 Slide template on work progress

Risk registry

The risk registry is a database of identified risks with the associated risk level analysis, an estimation of the risk occurrence, the review plan, and the history of their treatment.

The risk registry and classification are the first steps to analyze each risk. In the proposal, a critical risks and risk management strategy table was drafted based on likelihood and impact, both assessed with the same criteria: Low, Medium, and High. Since then, it has been completed with several elements to improve and support the monitoring:

- Definition of the overall risk level;
- Appointment of the risk owner and risk support;
- Estimation of the risk occurrence and consequence;
- Planning of the risk review dates.

A Google shared overview has been created to facilitate monitoring and collaboration between the Executive Committee (ExCom) and the concerned partner(s).

Risk #	1	2	3, etc....
Identification	DoA	DoA	
Work Package No(s)	All	WP1	
Risk title	One partner leaving the consortium	Difficult consortium management	
Risk owner	PCT	PCT	
Risk support	ExCOM	ExCOM	
Likelihood	Unlikely	Unlikely	
Impact	Moderate	Moderate	
Overall risk level	Low	Low	
Consequence of the risk occurrence	- Tasks and budget must be redistributed among existing or new beneficiary - Trigger risk #5	- Occurrence of conflicts - Potential difficulties to implement decision of the ExCom - Trigger risk #4, 5 and 10	
Proposed Mitigation Plan	Procedures for replacing a partner or redistribution of tasks described in the Consortium Agreement	The roles and responsibilities of each partner are defined in the Consortium Agreement. Escalation procedure is in place.	
Risk review date 1	Sept 2023	Sept 2023	
Identified threat(s) during risk review			
Result of the risk assessment	not assessed yet	not assessed yet	
Next risk review date	June 2024	June 2024	

Table 3 Risk registry

3.3. Risk Analysis

The risk is calculated according to the likelihood and impact matrix. The risk level set in the proposal has been further elaborated.

In the proposal:

Likelihood	Impact
Low	Low
Medium	Medium
High	High

In the current risk matrix:

Likelihood	
Unlikely	Unlikely to occur in the project's lifetime
Possible	Possible to occur in the first year of the project
Likely	Likely to occur in the first 6 months of the project
Almost certain	Almost certain to occur in the first quarter of the project
Impact	
Minor	Acceptable
Moderate	The effect is felt but not critical to the results
Major	Severe impact to the plan of action and results
Catastrophic	Could jeopardise the project

The risk likelihood and the impact form a grid that maps the probability of the risk occurrence and the effect on the project objectives in case the risk materializes. It results in the definition of the overall risk level, where “Low” means acceptable, “Medium” means reasonably manageable, “High” means generally unacceptable, and “Extreme” means intolerable.

Likelihood	Impact			
	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic
Unlikely	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Possible	Low	Medium	High	High
Likely	Medium	High	High	Extreme
Almost certain	Medium	High	Extreme	Extreme

Table 4 Risk Matrix

3.4. Risk mitigation

Risk mitigation or risk response will define the actions to avoid the risk or minimise its impact. The PCT will decide to accept the risk or define an avoidance or mitigation action plan. Each avoidance or mitigation action plan is recorded in the risk registry and reviewed.

3.5. Risk control & review

A dedicated review is performed for each risk at M9 and M18, with an update in the EC continuous reporting portal planned at each periodic report.

Risk level	Risk review	Response to the risk
Low	at least once per reporting period	Accept and monitor
Medium	at least once per year	Accept or mitigate and monitor
High	at least twice per year	Mitigate, define treatment and review contingency plan
Extreme	min one time per quarter	Avoid or mitigate, define recovery and review contingency plan

Table 5 Risk Control

The result of the risk assessment will be recorded in the risks registry as follows:

not assessed yet ▼

Accepted/Mitigation measure sufficient ▼

Temporarily accepted/Mitigation measures insufficient ▼

Treatment required ▼

4. Conclusion and next steps

The resources of the project coordination team and the project manager were focused on implementing the structure, procedures, tools, and guidelines needed to ensure efficient and transparent project management, with maximum information available to the consortium from the start of the project.

The project will review KPIs and risks during month 9 and present them to the General Assembly before the first project review. In project period 2, the project will continue the application of the quality plan. It will address project periodic review recommendations, adapting metrics, KPIs, and risks as needed.

Appendix 1 - deliverable checklist, guidelines for author and reviewer

Created by Celine Bitoune
Last updated: Mar 01, 2023

Content

- Does the deliverable include an acronym table? a definition table?
- Does the document contain an “Executive summary” and can it be read separately?
- Does the document contain an “Introduction” and is it well structured with a plan?
 - Avoid being too generic, or copy-paste from the DoA impact section.
- Is the scope and content of the deliverable in line with the deliverable description in the DoA?
 - If it isn't, is this properly justified, and what is the (new) plan?
- Are the objectives of the deliverable clearly stated?
 - and is the content consistent with its objectives?
- Is the scientific/technical approach sound and adequate?
- Is the quantity of data/information presented adequately?
- Does the content justify the length?
- Are the figures and tables all necessary and correctly referenced?
- Are the figures and tables complete (e.g. content, numbers and captions), clearly presented and of good quality?
- Do statistics and metrics refer to the target or any other information to understand the figures provided?
 - Eg measures expressed following the BTS model (base-target-stretch) with 3 figures respectively for the minimal, realistic and optimist scenarios, except for those where the number is 1, of course.
- Are key performance indicators (KPIs) identified? And are they relevant for the project and identifiable for the project?
 - Eg if unique users/followers/visitors is mentioned, make sure that it is possible to identify them specifically for the project
 - KPIs aren't simple metrics but a combination of several metrics that tell you how you are progressing towards your goal(s). For example audience is the metric that one will use to measure dissemination within several stakeholder groups, and to assess impact (KPI) according to the type of audience. This information will serve to adapt your dissemination strategy.
- Are the references cited relevant and up to date?
 - Does the document history mention all the contributors?
 - Are all the cited references linked with the source in the footer or as hyperlinks?
 - Do hyperlinks and references work?

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

- Is the deliverable written in British English, with good syntax and grammar, and adequate language for the target group(s)? Are grammar and spelling checks ok?
- Does the document include a conclusion?

Quality control & format

- The correct template is used
- The title, numbers, type and dissemination level are aligned with the DoA?
- The Format is consistent (numbering, font type, font size, colours, tables and graphs, images)?
- The deliverable includes an acronym table (symbols or abbreviations used in the deliverable are listed or referenced in the footer?)
- The document identification is completed and aligned with the DoA and key words are provided
- The document history and quality control are properly filled in
- The Dissemination level is accurate
- The table of contents is up-to-date (it's an easy-to-forget one!)
- Links are clickable and in the page footers
- Images, Graph, tables are clear and readable
- Grammar and typos are checked
- The document is saved under the correct filename "Palomera_DX.X vX_status"

The deliverable is saved:

- in the shared drive
- posted in Confluence
- and Zenodo or other open platforms as appropriate
- the upload into the EU portal is successful

Appendix 2 - PM01 Deliverable and milestones review

Document Control

Type	Project management (quality)
Purpose	The procedure describes steps by steps drafting, review and submission of deliverables and milestones
Owner	Celine Bitoune
Status	Version 1 - 31 Mar 2023
Next Review	during preparation of Periodic period 1 - 01 Sep 2023

Table of Content

- Overview
- Definitions
- Entities involved in the procedure
- Triggers
- Deliverables
 - Phase 1 - Preparation
 - Phase 2 - Quality phase
 - Phase 3 - EC approval
- Milestones

Overview

The formal outputs from the project (milestones and deliverables) go through a formal review process. The review process provides staged deadlines during the process to ensure the output is available to the European Commission at the end of the project month (PM) that the material is due.

For all deliverables, the status is indicated in the list of deliverable Deliverables.

Entities involved in the procedure

Lead author: The person from the activity and the partner responsible for the document and collecting input from relevant project tasks. They may rely on others within the activity to provide and/or collect the information needed. The Lead author and co-authors cannot be reviewers.

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM): Responsible for the review of milestones and deliverables. Check if the deliverable/milestone covered all needed topics and if the status of work presented in the document is according to the plan. Provides administrative support for the process.

Scientific Coordinator (SCO): Responsible for the review of milestones and deliverables. Check if the deliverable/milestone covered all needed topics and the status of work presented in the document is according to the plan.

Work Package leader (WP leader): Responsible for overseeing document production. The Work Package leader will work with the Lead author and co-authors to ensure that the work is done in a timely manner, and report to the PM on its progress.

Reviewers must not contribute to the deliverable to perform an independent, non-biased assessment.

Internal reviewer: appointed from within the WP.

External reviewer: appointed from outside the WP, from within the consortium or from external Board, such as Advisory Board in Palomera, or from OPERAS' coordination team¹¹.

- Deliverable: 2 reviewers - names delivered by WP leader and review role should be agreed a priori and informing the PM by email
- Milestone: PM and one member of the SCO
- Everyone working for Palomera can be appointed as a reviewer as part of their duties.

Triggers

6-8 weeks before the deadline for milestones/deliverables.

Deliverables

Phase 1 - Preparation

Steps	Responsible & Action	Status
Step 1 6-8 weeks before deadline	Lead Author <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prepares the Table of Content • shares it with WP Leader 	DRAFTING
Step 2 6-8 weeks before deadline	Lead Author, WP Leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose reviewers • Check availability of reviewers 	DRAFTING

¹¹ <https://operas-eu.org/about/governance-schema/coordination-team/>

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

Step 3 5-7 weeks before deadline	Lead author, WP leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works on the draft • in case of delay, WP leader informs Project coordination team (PCT) palomera-pct@operas-eu.org 	DRAFTING
Step 4 3-6 weeks before deadline	Lead author, WP leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notify reviewer(s), PCT in copy, palomera-pct@operas-eu.org, and provides the document in the email • Confirm the expected review completion date with reviewers and explain what is expected (see guidelines reviewer 	INTERNAL REVIEW or EXTERNAL REVIEW
Step 5 2-4 weeks before deadline	Reviewers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide review via email for the deliverable document - comments and improvement suggestions 	-
Step 6 2 weeks before deadline	Lead Author <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applies changes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Involves WP leader and PCT in case of conflicting reviews • Notifies the WP leader and PCT palomera-pct@operas-eu.org that an updated document is available • Circulates the final version to reviewers for their final comments 	DRAFTING
Step 7 1 week before deadline	Reviewers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approve the final version <p>In case of divergent opinion, the lead author will inform the WP leader and together they will decide on how to proceed with the comments to finalise the deliverable, involving or not the WP members, as they find it relevant.</p>	-
Step 8 1 week before deadline	WP leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notifies PCT palomera-pct@operas-eu.org that the document has completed a review and provide the document in the email • The review is complete 	READY FOR SUBMISSION

Phase 2 - Quality phase

Step 9 1 week before deadline	<p>Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM)</p> <p>The first pages of the document (along with the header and footer) contain metadata that needs to be reviewed and completed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performs quality control, update the formatting document history • Generates a clean PDF version of the document • filename format: Palomera-Dx.x-Vx.x-Public or DMP-Status • Saves it in the document repository and upload the document in the EC portal 	Status in the document: Under EC review
Step 10	<p>WP 5 leader</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uploads the deliverable in Zenodo (Public deliverables only) • Informs OPERAS Communication manager about submitted public deliverables 	SUBMITTED TO EC

Phase 3 - EC approval

The deliverables are approved altogether with the periodic report at each reporting period.

Step 1 EC approval	<p>Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM) /WP5 leader</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates the document in document repository and Zenodo (Public deliverables) 	Status in the document: Final
Step 2 EC rejection	<p>Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extracts EC comment(s) on the deliverable and insert them in the document history • Requests the author to provide a new version +1.0 <p>Go to step 3</p>	Status in the document: Drafting

Milestones

In this process, the reviewers' team comprises the PM and/or one member of the PCT.

Steps	Responsible & Action	Status
Step 1 3 weeks before deadline	WP Leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works on the milestone delivery • Informs Project coordination team (PCT) palomera-pct@operas-eu.org about the status and potential delays 	DRAFTING
Step 2 2 weeks before deadline	WP Leader <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informs Project coordination team (PCT) palomera-pct@operas-eu.org that the milestone is ready for review and: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Defines the means of verification, where and how the reviewers can obtain information for the indicators. 	INTERNAL REVIEW
Step 3 2 weeks before deadline	Project Coordination Team (PCT) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PM performs quality review • SCO performs the content review • Inform the WP leader on the outcome of the review 	DRAFTING
Step 4 1 week before deadline	If rejected: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP Leader applies corrections and changes Go to step 1 If accepted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PM marks done the milestone in the EC portal 	DRAFTING
Step 5	Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informs OPERAS Communication manager about submitted public deliverables 	SUBMITTED TO EC

Appendix 3 - PM02 intermediate and Periodic Reporting

Document Control

Type	Project management (reporting)
Purpose	The procedure describes steps by steps the reporting procedures.
Owner	Celine Bitoune
Status	Version 1 – 5 Jun 2023
Next Review	during preparation of Periodic report - 01 Sep 2023

Table of content

- Overview
- Entities involved in the procedure
- Reporting schedule
- Planning
 - Phase 1 - Reporting in the project management tool EUFIN
 - Phase 2 - Internal review WP Leaders (in preparation)
 - Phase 3 - Submission Periodic Reports (in preparation)

Overview

EU-fin <https://eufin-projectmanagement.eu/Palomera/Default.aspx> is the project reporting tool to monitor efforts consumption and project costs. One to two persons from each partner and 3rd party will be granted access to the tool. The list of people pre-defined includes all members of the financial mailing list.

Entities involved in the procedure

Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM): Responsible for the review of the reports. Check if the resource and the status of work reported are according to the plan. Provides administrative support for the process.

Scientific Coordinator (SCO): Responsible for the review of the reports. Check if the resource and the status of work reported are according to the plan.

Work Package leader (WP leader): Responsible to produce the periodic report. The Work Package leader will work with the task leaders and participants to ensure that the activity and deviations if any are accurately reported in the document and use of the resource is justified.

Reporting schedule

Frequency	Timeline
M1-M6: intermediate 6-month report	estimate efforts and personnel costs used due at M6+20 days; 20 July 2023
M1-M9: first Periodic report RP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • actual effort due at M09+20 days; 20 Oct 2023 • actual costs used due at M09+30 days; 30 Oct 2023 • submission date deadline to EC: 30 Nov 2023
M10-M18: Intermediate 6 months report	estimate efforts and personnel costs used due at M18+20 days; 20 July 2024 for underspending partners (release of 2nd instalment of prefinancing in case of underspending at RP1)
M10-M24: second Periodic report RP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • actual effort due at M24+20 days; 20 Jan 2025 • actual costs used due at M24+30 days; 30 Jan 2025 • submission date deadline to EC: 28 Feb 2025

Planning

Phase 1 - Reporting in the project management tool EUFIN

Steps	Responsible & Action
1	Login on the website https://eufin-projectmanagement.eu/OPERAS/ ! Password must be changed at first login.
2	Check your planned budget under the menu “Planning Budgets” By clicking on the headline (marked with an “i”) you will find information/guidance notes. if you spot any deviation, please contact palomera-pct@operas-eu.org .
3	Report the person months consumed under the menu “Reporting costs” By clicking on the headline (marked with an “i”) you will find a detailed description of how to enter and save your data.
4	Extract your data in excel under the menu “Pivot (tables)” By clicking on the headline (marked with an “i”) you will find information/guidance notes. you can create your own overview and extract it in excel; it will only display the data of the beneficiary.
5	WP leaders can oversee the use of resource for your WP, extract graph and table under the menu “Dashboards” Information/guidance notes are available by clicking on the headline (marked with an “i”).

Phase 2 - Internal review WP Leaders (in preparation)

Steps	Responsible & Action	Prerequisite if any
1	PCT and ExCOM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define and communicate timeline for data reporting, - appoint responsible person. 	
2	Project Manager <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prepares pivot tables of the person months and budget used during the first period, - calculates the deviation compared to the budget plan (KPI4 and 5). 	
3	ExCOM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reviews potential deviations against the plan in the DoA, - appoints responsible person to gather feedback from partners concerned. 	

Phase 3 - Submission Periodic Reports (in preparation)

Steps	Responsible & Action	Prerequisite if any
1	PCT and ExCOM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define and communicate timeline for drafting the narrative part of the periodic report, - appoint responsible persons. 	
2	Project Manager <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prepare a shared google doc using the latest template of the periodic reporting. 	
3	WP Leaders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - draft the narrative part, Project Manager <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - include the table of the use of resources and report on the deviations. 	
4	Scientific coordinator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - review the periodic report. - consolidate the narrative part. 	
5	Project Manager <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - submit a consolidate periodic report reviewed by the ExCom (Par A and B). 	

Appendix 4 – EU-fin project management guidelines

Planning

To plan the person-months follow the next steps:

Select participant :

Select work package :

Planning Overview

No zero rows

Whole duration Budget Personnel Costs									
Task	PM	1 Percentage EC	2 Average PM	3 Start Month	End Month	Total Direct	Total Indirect	Old Versions	
T01.01 - Taskname	0	70	8500	1	36	0,00	0,00		
T01.02 - Taskname	4	70	8500	1	36	23.800,00	5.950,00		
T01.03 - Taskname	9	70	8500	1	36	53.550,00	13.387,50		
T01.04 - Taskname	2	70	8500	1	36	11.900,00	2.975,00		
						89.250,00	22.312,50		
15,00						89.250,00	22.312,50		

1. Percentage EC contribution is the default value entered for the selected participant;
2. Average (AVG) person month (PM) rate is the default value entered for the selected participant;
3. Start and End date are the defaults entered for the task. Min and max values are the start and End month from the WP;

All the columns can be changed per record are different values possible.

Reporting

To report person-months follow the next steps:

The screenshot shows the EU-fin reporting interface. The left sidebar contains a menu with 'Reporting Costs' highlighted. The main area has three dropdown menus: 'Select participant:' (P01: Participant 1), 'Select Interim period:' (IP1.1 M1 - M6; 01/01/2020; 06/30/2020;), and 'Select work package:' (WP01: Innovation Management). The 'Status interim period:' is set to 'Open'. Below these are tabs for 'Personnel costs', 'Sub contracting', 'Travel costs', and 'Other direct costs'. A table displays reporting data with columns for Function / Category, Task, SME owner hours, PM used, Total PMs costs, and Description. Two rows are visible: one with 'fff' and '690' (Total PMs costs: 14,500.00) and another with 'xvvv' and '691' (Total PMs costs: 7,540.00). The bottom of the interface includes 'Preview changes', 'Save changes', and 'Cancel changes' buttons, along with a footer containing '© 2020 Navigator Europe' and 'Privacy Policy'.

1. Select the menu option Reporting/reporting costs;
2. Select the desired reporting period. Its status should be "Open", otherwise you cannot enter data;
3. Select the work package for which you want to report;
4. Select the expenditure type tab "Personnel costs" (is default selected);
5. Enter the person-months per individual and for a given period and work package.

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

1 New	Function / Category	Task	SME owner hours	PM used	Total PMs costs	If you use Unit costs, tick this box	Description
Delete	svdfsfs 2	Task 3.1		3,00	333,00	<input type="checkbox"/>	dvsdvs
Delete	cdxaz aa	Task 3.1		2,00	222,00	<input type="checkbox"/>	sdvsdv

3

[Preview changes](#)
[Save changes](#)
[Cancel changes](#)

1. Create a new row by clicking “New” link;
2. Add the name of the involved person, Person months and total costs; (Use a point as decimal separator);
3. Click “Save changes”
4. Repeat those actions until all person months records have been inserted and filled in.
5. Repeat the above actions for every work package your institute is involved into.

Select work package:

- WP1 Specifications definition
- WP2 Materials and components optimisation
- WP3 Stack design and engineering
- WP4 Higreew battery prototype engineering
- WP6 Safety and Environmental Issues
- WP7 Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy
- WP8 Project coordination and management

